

A PROSPECTIVE COMMUNITY BASED OBSERVATIONAL STUDY TO ASSESS KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE TOWARDS ANTIBIOTICS USAGE IN RURAL POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Antibiotics are the chemotherapeutic agents that kill or inhibit the growth of bacteria, that are useful in treating bacterial infections in humans and animals. Antibiotics played an important role in the remarkable increase in life expectancy in the latter half of the 20th century. Antibiotics are classified based on the activity, spectrum of action. Mode of action, source, and chemical structure. Based on action, these are divided into Bacteriostatic and Bactericidal Antibiotics. Inappropriate use, misuse, and excessive use of antibiotics lead to antibiotic resistance, which is a serious global health issue.

Methodology: This study is a community based observational study conducted at Yallamanda, Narasaraopet by enrolling 200 members who met inclusion and exclusion criteria and assessments were performed using a structured KAP questionnaires that were extracted from NIH, WHO, ICMR, and from standard published literature. **Results:** A total of 200 responses were analysed. After analysing all these studies, it was clear that 69.5% had good knowledge about Antibiotics

while 93.50% had positive attitudes and 83.00% had good practices. **Conclusion:** The study sheds light on the urgent necessity for continuous community-based health education

programs aimed at raising awareness and knowledge as well as instilling rational antibiotic use practices among people who are at the lowest levels in terms of education and income. Public enlightenment and antibiotic use regulation would, on the one hand, provide the first line of defence against the misuse of antibiotics and, on the other hand, help curb the growing menace of antimicrobial resistance.

KEYWORDS: Mode of action, source, chemical structure, Antibiotics, narrow & broad spectrum antibiotics, MOA, KAP.

INTRODUCTION

Antibiotics are the chemotherapeutic agents that kill or inhibit the growth of bacteria, that are useful in treating bacterial infections in humans and animals.^[1]

The term antibiotics was defined by Selman A. Waksman in 1947 as these are synthesized from microorganisms and these are capable to inhibit the growth and kills the same bacteria and their microorganisms.^[2] The word “Antibiotics” describes compounds that are naturally occurring from a variety of microorganisms such as bacteria and fungus which are capable to inhibit the growth of other microorganisms and kill their cells.

Antibiotics possess a wide range of applications in different sectors such as human health, agriculture, livestock breeding, and fish farms.^[3] Antibiotics played an important role in the remarkable increase in life expectancy in the latter half of the 20th century.

The bacteria were first identified in the year 1670’s by Antony van leu-van Hoek following his investigation with his microscope. French scientist Trofuel who demonstrated that specific bacterial strains were crucial to fermentation. Listen introduced a carbolic acid as an antiseptic and sterilizing agent for operation theatres and wards.

Alexander Fleming discovered penicillin in 1928, which marked a turning point in the development of antimicrobial medication. In 1897, Ernest Duchesne reported penicillium species antibacterial qualities in France. During 1940s–1960s Waksman initiated the Golden Age of antibiotics.^[3]

From 1930s to 2004s wide variety of antibiotics have been discovered like Sulphonamides, Prontosil, streptomycin, Bacitracin, Cefacetrile, Tetracycline, Colistin, Trimethoprim, Isoniazid, various classes of aminoglycosides, Fusidic acid, Clindamycin, and various

antibiotics that are used to treat Urinary Tract Infections, Respiratory Tract Infections and effective against wide range of infections and open wounds and till now many novel antibiotics has been discovering.^[4]

Classification of antibiotics

Antibiotics are classified based on the activity, spectrum of action. Mode of action, source and chemical structure.

Based on action, these are divided into Bacteriostatic and Bactericidal Antibiotics.

The Bacteriostatic antibiotics are the agents which inhibit the growth of the bacteria without killing them. E.g. **Tetracyclines** (Doxycycline, Tetracycline, Minocycline), **Glycylcyclines** (Tigecycline), **Macrolides** (Azithromycin, Erythromycin, Clarithromycin), **Lincosamides** (Clindamycin), **Oxazolidinones** (Linezolid), **Chloramphenicol**, **Sulphonamides** (Sulfamethoxazole), **Nitrofurans** (Nitrofurantoin) and Fusidic Acid.

The Bactericidal antibiotics are the agents that kills the bacteria by disrupting cell wall, inhibiting cell wall or membrane synthesis and inhibiting DNA replication. E.g. **Penicillins** (Penicillin-G, Amoxicillin), **Cephalosporins** (Cefuroxime, Cefixime), **Carbapenems** (Imipenem, Meropenem), **Monobactams** (Aztreonam), **Fluoroquinolones** (Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, Moxifloxacin), **Aminoglycosides** (Gentamycin, Tobramycin, Streptomycin, Amikacin), **Glycopeptides** (Vancomycin), **Cyclic Lipopeptides** (Daptomycin), **Nitroimidazole** (Metronidazole), **Rifamycin** (Rifampin), **Sulfonamides** (Cotrimoxazole) and **Phosphonic Acid Derivative** (Fosfomicin).^[5,6,7,8]

Mechanism of action of antibiotics

Antibiotics acts through one of five mechanisms: interfering with bacterial cell wall synthesis [beta-lactams (penicillin and its derivatives, cephalosporins and carbapenems) and glycopeptides (vancomycin)], inhibition of bacterial protein biosynthesis [30S (aminoglycosides and tetracyclines) or 50S (chloramphenicol, macrolides, and oxazolidinones) subunit], inhibition of bacterial nucleic acid synthesis (rifamycin and fluoroquinolones), inhibition of metabolic pathways (Sulfonamides and trimethoprim), and inhibition of bacterial membrane function [Polymyxins(Colistin and Polymyxin B) and Daptomycin].^[9]

The KAP is a representative survey conducted in a particular population to identify the knowledge (K), attitudes (A) and practices (P) of a population on a specific topic. **Knowledge** refers to the information, awareness, and understanding a person has about a particular subject or issue. **Attitude** refers to a person's feelings, beliefs, opinions, and perceptions toward a subject, which influence their willingness to act. **Practice** refers to the actual actions or behaviors a person follows in real-life situations related to the subject.^[10,11,12]

Antibiotics are vital for the treatment of bacterial infections. However, inappropriate use, misuse, and excessive use of antibiotics lead to antibiotic resistance, which is a serious global health issue.

The major reasons for antibiotic resistance include self-medication, taking incorrect dosages, not completing the prescribed course of antibiotics, and unnecessary use of antibiotics for prophylaxis lead to treatment failure, increased medical expenses, drug side effects, and the spread of bacterial resistance.

Antibiotic resistance occurs when broad-spectrum antibiotics are administered instead of narrow-spectrum antibiotics when not required. This leads to increased exposure of bacteria to antibiotics, causing bacteria to develop resistance mechanisms such as changes in cell walls, cell membranes, and production of enzymes that destroy antibiotics.

Therefore, conducting a KAP study on antibiotic usage is very important for early identification of gaps and misconceptions, as well as for encouraging rational use of antibiotics. The results of this study could be a point of reference for future surveys and intervention programs for promoting rational use of antibiotics and in fighting antibiotic resistance.^[13,14,15,16]

AIM

To assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to antibiotic use among the rural population and to identify the gaps that may contribute to inappropriate antibiotic use and antibiotic resistance.

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the level of knowledge of the rural population regarding indications, dosage, duration, and completion of antibiotic therapy.

- To evaluate the attitudes of the rural population toward self-medication, expectations for the antibiotics and use of antibiotics for common illness such as cold and fever.
- To assess the practices related to antibiotic use such as source of antibiotics, frequency of antibiotic consumption, and compliance with prescribed medication.
- To determine whether better knowledge and attitude with respect to antibiotics affected the practices relating to their use.

METHODOLOGY

Study site: This study was conducted at Yallamanda, Narasaraopet.

Study period: The study will be conducted over a period of 4 months.

Study design: This is an observational study.

Sample size: A total of 200 participants from the rural community were included in the study. Participants who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected and used in the study.

Study criteria

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- People who are between 18–65 years of age were included in this study.
- People who had used antibiotics at least once in the past and were aware of antibiotic usage are included in this study.
- Both male and female participants.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- People who are not interested in participating in the study were excluded.
- People with ages less than 18 years and above 60 years are excluded.
- Health care professionals (i.e., doctors, nurses, pharmacists) are excluded.
- People who are unable to communicate effectively or complete the questionnaire.

RESULTS

Fig- 1 Distribution based on Age of study population

AGE	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
18-22	12	6.00%
23-27	14	7.00%
28-32	14	7.00%
33-37	22	11.00%
38-42	33	16.50%
43-47	14	7.00%
48-52	16	8.00%
53-57	27	13.50%
58-62	28	14.00%
63-65	20	10.00%
Grand Total	200	100.00%

Table- 1: Distribution based on Age of study population

The data reveals that the highest KAP of Antibiotics use is observed in 38-42 age group of 16.5%(n=33). Followed by the 58-62 age group with 14% (n=28), and the 53-57 age group with n=27 (13.5%). 32-37 age group includes n=22 (11%), 48-52 age group has n=16 (8%), 23-27, 28-32, 43-47 age groups have n=14 (7%), and 18-22 age group with 6% (n=12).

Fig- 2 Distribution based on Gender of study population

GENDER	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
Female	102	51
Male	98	49
Grand Total	200	100

Table-2: Distribution based on Gender

The data represents the KAP of Antibiotics use based on the gender is as out of the total 102 participants (51%) are Females whereas Males with 49%.

Fig- 3 Distribution based on Education of study population

EDUCATION	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
Graduate	40	20.00%
Illiterate	55	27.50%
PG	6	3.00%
Primary	64	32.00%
Secondary	35	17.50%
Grand Total	200	100.00%

Table- 3: Distribution based on Education

The data represents the literacy distribution among a total of 200 participants. Out of the total, 63 participants (32%) were having their primary education while a significantly larger group of 55 participants (27.5%) were illiterate. 40 Participant (20%) completed their graduation. Some of where have completed their secondary education (n=35) is 17.5% and only 6 participants were pursuing their PG (3%).

Fig- 4 Distribution based on Occupation of study population

OCCUPATION	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
Business	31	15.50%
Driver	3	1.50%
Electrician	1	0.50%
Farmer	71	35.50%
Home maker	47	23.50%
Job	23	11.50%
Labour	10	5.00%
Lecturer	1	0.50%
Student	12	6.00%
Tailor	1	0.50%
Grand Total	200	100.00%

Table- 4: Distribution based on occupation

The data represents the occupation distribution among a total of 200 participants. Out of the total, among Farmer, accounting for 35.50% (n=71), followed by Homemakers at 23.50% (n=47), Business at 15.50% (n=31), Job holders at 11.5% (n=23), while students represented 6% (n=12), drivers with 1.50% (n=3). Additionally, Electrician, tailor, lectures, professionals each accounted for 0.50%(n=1).

Fig- 5 Distribution based on Income of study population

INCOME	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
<5000	47	23.50%
5000-10000	75	37.50%
>10000	19	9.50%
NO INCOME	59	29.50%
Grand Total	200	100.00%

Table- 5: Distribution based on Income

The data represents the income distribution among 200 selected participants, most of the participants were earning 5000-10000 (n=75), 37.50%, while the fewest were earning more than 10000 (n=19, 9.50). Unfortunately, 59 participants were with no income sources. Additionally, 47 participants were with < 5000 per month (23.50%).

Fig- 6 Distribution based on Knowledge of study population

KNOWLEDGE	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
Poor	60	30.00%
Good	139	69.50%
Excellent	1	0.50%
Grand Total	200	100.00%

Table- 6: Distribution based on Knowledge

The data shows that most participants had good knowledge $n=139$ (69.50%). Followed by poor knowledge has $n=60$ (30%), fewer with excellent knowledge has $n=1$ (0.5%).

Fig- 7 Distribution based on Attitude of study population

ATTITUDE	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
Poor	13	6.50%
Good	187	93.50%
Grand Total	200	100.00%

Table-7: Distribution based on Attitude

The data shows that most participants had good attitude $n=187$ (93.50%). Followed by poor attitude has $n=13$ (6.50%).

Fig- 8 Distribution based on Practice of study population

PRACTICE RANGE	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
Poor	31	15.50%
Good	166	83.00%
Excellent	3	1.50%
Grand Total	200	100.00%

Table- 8: Distribution based on Practice

The data shows that most participants had good Practice $n=166$ (83.00%). Followed by Poor Practice has $n=31$ (15.5%), fewer with excellent Practice has $n=3$ (1.50%).

Fig- 9 Distribution based on KAP of study population

KAP	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
Good	78	39.00%
Moderate	121	60.50%
Poor	1	0.50%
Grand Total	200	100.00%

Table- 9: Distribution based on overall KAP

The data shows that a significant portion of participants, 121 individuals (60.50%), were classified as having moderate KAP score, indicating that more than half of the population demonstrated good levels of Knowledge, Attitude and Practice. The next largest group 78 participants (39.00%) had good KAP score suggesting that many patients perform at a moderate level in these areas. Only one participant (0.5%) were classified as having a poor KAP score, reflecting a very small portion with higher knowledge attitude and practice. This distribution emphasizes that most participants fall within the good to moderate range in terms of KAP.

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) regarding antibiotic usage among individuals residing in a rural community. This study included 200 participants, of whom the female and male ratio is almost equal (51% females and 49% males). Most participants belonged to the 38–42 years age group (16.5%), indicating an economically productive segment of the rural population.

The educational background of the participants showed that 27.5% were illiterate, and the largest part had primary schooling (32%). Only 17.5% received secondary education, 20% were graduates, and merely 3% had a postgraduate degree. Such a trend shows that although there is a basic level of literacy in the community, higher education is lacking. These educational constraints are a feature of most rural areas and may curb the community's knowledge and awareness of rational antibiotic use.

Regarding occupation, most of the people were farmers (35.5%), followed by homemakers (23.5%) and businessmen (15.5%). As far as income is concerned, the participants portrayed a lower-middle-class image with 37.5% earning between ₹5000 and ₹10000 monthly, 23.5%

earning less than ₹5000, 29.5% without any income, and only 9.5% earning over ₹10000 per month. Different socioeconomic factors may result in issues regarding the participants' capability to get the healthcare, their behaviour in seeking treatments, and their medication, especially antibiotic, use practices.

Knowledge: 69.5% of the respondents were evaluated to have good knowledge, only 0.5% excellent knowledge, and 30% had poor knowledge of antibiotic use. However, the mere fact that nearly one-third of the respondents had poor knowledge is a matter of concern.

When people do not have enough knowledge, they may use antibiotics inappropriately, for instance, they self-medicate, take antibiotics for viral infections, stop the medication therapy too soon when symptoms get better, or are not aware that misuse of antibiotics causes resistance of microorganisms.

Attitude: The attitude assessment found a large majority (93.5%) of the respondents holds a positive attitude in using antibiotics, while a minority (6.5%) showed a negative one. The large majority of good attitudes indicate that most people understand the importance of responsible antibiotic use and may be open to receiving advice from healthcare professionals. On the other hand, having a good attitude is not always sufficient to give correct behaviours especially in the absence of adequate knowledge and strengthening of the concept.

Practice: Results from the practice part showed that 83% of the respondents were scored with good practices, 15.5% with poor practices, and 1.5% with excellent practices in the use of antibiotics. About most respondents reported appropriate antibiotic use practices. However, poor practices are performed by a notable part of the population, thus the presence of this segment of the population poses the risk of continuous incomplete antibiotic courses, self-medication, sharing of antibiotics, and improper dosages. Such behaviours contribute to antimicrobial resistance, treatment failure, and an increased burden on health care.

The overall KAP evaluation revealed that 60.5% of participants had moderate KAP scores, 39% had good scores, and only 0.5% had poor KAP levels. The predominance of moderate KAP implies that, even though the rural community has awareness and positive attitudes, knowledge and practices are not yet comprehensive. These present situations necessitate the

increase of educational interventions to help the public understand better and adopt consistent rational drug use behaviours.

The findings point to the significance of community-based health educational programs in a village environment. Misconceptions about antibiotics might stem from poor health care access and heavy reliance on friends or family as information sources. There upon, pharmacists' advice, primary health workers' involvement, and formalized health education could be keys in promoting the rational use of antibiotics, thereby, eventually, favouring antibiotic stewardship. Besides other vulnerable groups, those with low-level education and low-income status should be facilitated in health awareness equitably.

CONCLUSION

A prospective community-based observational study was conducted among a rural population to assess knowledge, attitude, and practice towards antibiotic use. A great majority of the study participants (69.5%) had good knowledge, 93.5% showed positive attitude, and 83% had good practices regarding antibiotic usage. Nevertheless, quite many people exhibited poor knowledge (30%) and poor practices (15.5%) which clearly indicates that there are still awareness and behaviour gaps that need to be addressed.

Overall KAP assessment showed that majority of the participants had moderate levels of KAP (60.5%) which means that there is some level of awareness, but it is not complete. Such gaps might be the reason or one of the reasons why antibiotics are used irrationally which results in antimicrobial resistance.

The study sheds light on the urgent necessity for continuous community-based health education programs aimed at raising awareness and knowledge as well as instilling rational antibiotic use practices among people who are at the lowest levels in terms of education and income. Public enlightenment and antibiotic use regulation would, on the one hand, provide the first line of defence against the misuse of antibiotics and, on the other hand, help curb the growing menace of antimicrobial resistance.

Research in the future must be geared towards elucidating the factors behind the irrational antibiotic practices and on the other hand, assessing the long-term impact of targeted educational intervention in leading to improved antibiotic stewardship in rural communities.

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